

Research Article

ASSESSING PRINCIPALS' INVOLVEMENT IN YOUTH ICT AND ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILL ACQUISITION FOR JOB CREATION IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS, GWAGWALADA, ABUJA

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ABSTRACT

The paper examined principals' involvement in youth information communication technology and entrepreneurial skill acquisition for job creation in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada, Abuja, Nigeria. The researchers used survey research design for the study. The population of the study was 657 teachers from public senior secondary schools, Gwagwalada Area Council, FCT-Abuja. The sample of the study was 300 teachers sampled through random sampling technique (these teachers were used to assess the principals). Random sampling technique was applied to give all the respondents equal chance to participate in the study. Questionnaire on "Principals Involvement in Youths Acquisition of Information Communication Technological and Entrepreneurial Skills for Job Creation (PIYAICTESJC) was used to collect data for analysis. The instrument was validated by experts in the Computer Science and Economics Departments, University of Abuja. The reliability of the instrument was obtained by test-retest method and the analysed study was carried out by using Pearson Correlation Coefficient and Spearman Rho rank order correlation coefficients. The coefficient reliability index achieved was 0.71. Mean statistics were used to analyze the research questions. The findings revealed that the principals did not involve themselves in youth acquisition of information communication technological skills for job creation. The principals did not also involved themselves in the youths' acquisition of entrepreneurial skills for job creation in public senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada, FCT, Abuja. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended that the principals should ensure that the youths are well educated to acquire knowledge, skill and competence on ICT and entrepreneurship so as to be able to create jobs for themselves and others in the society. This will make these youths to be self-reliant, independent and relevant in the society. They should do this by ensuring that the schools have functional and enough equipment, facilities, qualified instructors, educational and material resources for ICT and entrepreneurship education to thrive and Government at any levels should encourage the schools management by supporting them with funds to make sure that ICT and entrepreneurship education is taken and executed seriously. The youths must be trained to be able to create jobs opportunities to boost the economy of the nation

Keyword: Principals, Skill Acquisition, Information Communication Technology Skill, Entrepreneurial Skill, Job Creation.

Introduction

Youth education is crucial for obtaining skills in different fields of human endeavors. The development of any country's economy is highly dependent on youths. Youth is a critical period in an individual' lifespan, because this is the stage when one should be empowered and equipped with skills such as entrepreneurial and academic skills that will

be needed in future life. Nigerian youths need technical, Information and Communication Technology (ICT), and academic skills for empowerment to be able to create jobs, be independent and relevant in the society. Principals of secondary schools as a matter of priority and need must make sure that there is provision of ICT facilities and resources to engage these young ones in entrepreneurship

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training for them to be equipped for job creation. Principals must ensure provision of ICT facilities and resources, as educational planning by school leaders directly enables functional infrastructure in Gwagwalada schools (Ebuk & Bankole, 2019; Mohammed & Ebuk, 2023; Abdulrahman & Adegrooye, 2025). They should ensure that these youths do not only acquire certificates but that they should have the knowledge, skills, competence and academic mastery that will enable them to create jobs for themselves and others. This will make them to be self-reliant and relevant to the society. Becoming employer of labor, contributing to enhance the nation's economic development is tantamount to being equipped with skills in ones field of labor. Amadi (2019) in support of the above statement opined that youths should acquire knowledge from all technological devices and other educative materials to boost entrepreneurship training for job creation and economic development.

Information Communication Technology (ICT) and Entrepreneurial Skills for Job Creation

Information Communication Technological and entrepreneurial skills can aid youths to create jobs which they can employ others. Ebuk and Abdullahi (2023) is of the opinion that if the youths engage in Lifelong learning programs in ICT and receive effective teaching and training and technical education they will create jobs for unemployed youths, be able to alleviate vices, eradicate militancy, crimes, kidnapping and other social vices which youths get themselves involved. The researchers also maintained that youths' education and training should include formal education and training programs in entrepreneurial activities to stimulate entrepreneurial attitudes. Technology is a device that reduces human suffering and enhances productivity for people to relax and

enjoy their environment better. Amadi (2019) asserted that technology is the use of scientific knowledge and ideas to carryout practical works in production of materials which can help in job creation. It can help in providing entrepreneurial information for youths to have knowledge to build their entrepreneurial base. The researcher further expressed that technology is required in production of a nation's economy because it is geared towards the economic well-being of human beings in the society. This is so because it can aid job creation and employment which can influence human life towards development. Knowledge and skills to create jobs which can sustain the youths to be relevant in the society can be gotten from ICT and entrepreneurial education (Adeyemo *et al.*, 2024).

Akpan (2019) identified ICT gadgets such as: scanners, hardware, software, laptops, digital cameras, CD-Roms, DVD players, radio, television, fax phones and data base programmes can provide information which can help youths in job creation. E-learning platforms enable youth to retrieve entrepreneurial information for job creation (Ebuk & Abdullahi, 2019). The researcher affirmed that these gadgets or electronics can help individuals to store, retrieve, organize, manipulate, present, exchange information crucial for any investments. Asonze and Nwadozie (2019) maintained that Whatsapp which is an ICT software is a very effective and efficient tool for staining information with clarity, it is a platform for exchanging opinions with ease and convenience provide feedback and increase confidence among the users. The youths therefore with this ICT platform can get vital information on any job activities of their choice, obtain the knowledge, which will help them create jobs independently. ICT channels such as the internet and browsers such as google chrome, can be applied by youths to get

information on entrepreneurial activities which can help them in job creation hence, having skill in ICT can really aid the youths in job creation.

Omode (2014) pointed out that Information Communication Technology has turned the whole world into a global village and has opened various channels of accessing information. ICT integration fundamentally transforms pedagogical approaches, enabling access to job-creation resources beyond physical classrooms (Chukwuemeka & Dominic, 2019; Chukwuemeka *et al.*, 2021). These channels have helped the youths to be knowledgeable on different activities that can help them create jobs for themselves and others. Akpan (2019) maintained that ICT has created awareness and understanding among the youths and other individuals, on their physical environment concerning the available resources. It has helped these youths to develop the ability to utilize these resources to create jobs to boost the economy for self-employment. Aboderin (2015) submitted that ICT empowers learners (youths and adults) with technology and scientific skills which are crucial to make them succeed in today's world to have global entrepreneurial skills for creating jobs.

Entrepreneurship has provided various skills which if the youths acquire these skills, will help them to create jobs for themselves and others. According to Fagge, Abdul & Mohammed (2019) entrepreneurship education cuts across all fields of studies and all levels of education. Valerio *et al.* (2014) have designated four areas of entrepreneurial skills. These are:

Entrepreneurial mindset: this is the socio-emotional skill and the overall awareness of entrepreneurship associated with entrepreneurial motivation and future success

of an entrepreneur. The skill revealed individuals self-confidence, leadership, creativity, risk propensity, motivation, resilience and self-efficacy.

Entrepreneurial capabilities: are skills which refer to the entrepreneurial competencies, knowledge and technical knowledge and skills associated with marketing.

Entrepreneurial status: this skill is based on an entrepreneur having the ability to start a new business, achieving a high income and becoming employer of labor.

Entrepreneurial performance skill: this refers explicitly to the entrepreneur having the ability to enhance his business, make high profits, increasing sales, employing people and creating higher survival rates for them. This skill brings changes as a result of the entrepreneur acquiring mastery in his skills.

Vesenyi (2016) affirmed that entrepreneurial skills can be achieved by learning, and engaging in the programmes which provide practical information and introduce the recipients to real life experiences. To this effect, Vesenyi advised that entrepreneurial programmes should be made to focus on the theories of what entrepreneurship is all about. Also, that in entrepreneur should focus on how to start and manage new and growing businesses or in creating and implementing new initiatives. Youths should acquire skill from learning from others, from case studies, through internship, learning from workshops/guest speakers and from experienced and knowledgeable entrepreneurs who have been operating for a long period of time. Skills can also be gotten from company visits, seeing and learning from practical life projects and more so through experience from self by starting a new venture or projects less of traditional lecturing.

The youths should be knowledgeable on the entrepreneurial skills which bothers on execution of right decision, ability to work with appropriate qualification, training of workers, grading, paying of workers' salaries, entitlements, implementing better conditions of services and in maintenance of rules and regulations. Youths should also acquire managerial skills to employ, terminate or dismiss workers from appointment. They should have the knowledge and expertise in controlling human beings, finances (or hire financial experts) and should see to it that things go normal for the operation and survival of the business. They should be skillful in risk bearing, take it in good faith when it occurs, provide security to safe guard the welfare of workers and themselves. Youths should be skillful on method of production that is available, affordable, that will yield profits, minimize losses and in finding best alternatives. Kwajaffa (2019) further posited that youths should be skillful in coordinating all the activities, programmes and schedules involved in the production cycle. They should be competent to assign responsibilities to staff, in reshuffling, preparation of duty schedules and in involving in the general welfare of the workers. Evaluation is an essential aspect in job establishment so in wanting to create jobs, youths should have the knowledge of how to evaluate. They should use techniques which will enable them to interpret progress or failure in business before finding solutions. They should be skillful in having good working relationship with employees and should develop corporate work ethics which will motivate them to be diligent, committed and self-sacrifice. They should be knowledgeable about their workers having life insurances, health facilities and conducive working environment. This will aid the youths to achieve the job objectives when creating any jobs. Hence, they must have the skill to

draw comprehensive objectives on specific or general factors pertaining to the jobs (Kwajaffa 2019). Ebuk & Olowonefa (2019) maintained that in creating jobs the youths should not only consider the employees but that they should appreciate the sovereignty of the consumers. The services or products they will render or produce should be such that are required by the individuals they are meant for. Creative resource organization is critical for sustaining youth-led enterprises (Afu & Ebuk, 2023).

In considering the ICT and entrepreneurial skills for youths job creation. Amadi (2019) stipulated that ICT can enable the youths to create, produce and have job opportunities. The youths according to Amadi can work as computer programmers, technicians, technologists, consultant in technology based activities. ICT is a system to speed up work and increase productivity. Amadi (2019) maintained that computer electronic devices are highly needed to make job easier and faster for the youth entrepreneurs. Also, having skills in ICT and entrepreneurship will make it easier and faster for the youths or any individuals to increase production on the job. The youths being skillful in ICT and entrepreneurship will help them to be creative, innovative and engage in job creation which can boost the nations' economy. Nwadozie (2019) affirmed that youths can utilize whatsapp to get clarifications from entrepreneurs on existing jobs and vital information for new job creation and formation. Adeyemo *et al.* (2024) maintained that ICT helped the users to be effective and brings operational improvement. Johnson, Adams, Cummins and Estrada (2023) posited that ITC helps youths to evaluate their success on projects and brings technological advancement.

Statement of the Problem

Youths should be exposed to formal, technical and vocational education for better acquisition of knowledge in these areas of endeavors. Schools therefore in preparing them must make sure that there are resources (human, materials found), facilities and better curriculum content to cater for their education. Youths being trained to have skills especially in information communication technology and entrepreneurship will help them to create jobs for themselves and others, it will reduce societal vices and crimes, help them to fend or provide for their families, become employer of labor and contribute to the nation's economy and development. This will make the youths not only to be independent but also to be self-reliant and relevant in the society. The study therefore lies on the principals of secondary schools that the youths are well trained to acquire skills in ICT and entrepreneurship so as to make sure the youths be able to create jobs even if it is online for individuals.

Purpose of the Study

The study is aimed at investigating whether principals are involved in youths acquiring information communication technological and entrepreneurial skills for job creation. Specifically, the researchers want to find out whether the principals are involved in youths acquiring:

1. Information communication technology and
2. Entrepreneurial skills for job creation

Research Questions

Two research questions were stated to guide the study:

1. Have principals in secondary schools involved in the youth acquisition of ICT skill for job creation in Public Schools, Gwagwalada, FCT, Abuja?

2. Have principals in secondary schools involved in the youth entrepreneurial skill acquisition for job creation in public secondary schools, Gwagwalada, FCT, Abuja?

Methodology

A survey research design was adopted for the study. The design helped them, to select representatives from the population as sample of the study (Nakpodia, 2010). Information was retrieved from the representatives to generate data for the study. The population of the study was 657 teachers from nine government senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, FCT Abuja. The sample drawn from this population was 300 teachers, through random sampling technique. A questionnaire titled 'Principals' Involvement in Youths Acquisition of Information Communication Technological and Entrepreneurial Skills for Job Creation' (PIYAICTESJC) was used for collection of data. Validation of the instrument was done by experts in ICT and Economic departments, University of Abuja, Nigeria. Data reliability was obtained through test-retest method and the data was using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Spearman RHO rank order correlation coefficient. The reliability index coefficient score of 0.71 was obtained showing that the instrument was reliable for the study. Mean statistics was used for research questions analysis, for research questions results, the mean of 2.50 and above were regarded as agreed whereas 2.49 and below were adjudged as disagreed.

Data Analysis:

Research Questions:

Research Question One: Have the principals involve the youths in the acquisition of information communication technological (ICT) skills for job creation in secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja?

Table 1: Principals Involvement in Youths Acquisition of Information Communication Technological Skills for Job Creation

S/N	Items on Principals Involvement in Youths Acquisition of Information Communication Technological Skills for Job Creation	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Decision
	Your principals have provided ICT facilities for you to:						
1.	Be exposed to information communication technological devices to empower you to have knowledge of job creation	40	34	130	96	2.06	Disagreed
2.	Acquire ICT knowledge and skills to carryout practical work independently in entrepreneurship to aid you in creating jobs	34	40	130	96	2.04	Disagreed
3.	Be trained to be competent in the usage of ICT for jobs creation	14	66	100	120	1.91	Disagreed
4.	Be trained to get information from Whatsapp to help you in job creation.	24	83	117	76	2.18	Disagreed
5.	Apply devices such as Google, Chrome, AI, GBT information on entrepreneurship for job creation	26	24	112	118	1.72	Disagreed
6.	Apply ICT device such as digital camera to televise and learn practical work which aids you in job creation	46	19	124	111	2.00	Disagreed
7.	Use devices like DVD player and CD Roms to help you to retrieve entrepreneurial information for job creation	44	23	123	102	1.98	Disagreed
8.	Acquire practical knowledge on how to store data in the data based programmed system to help you on job creation.	55	45	100	100	2.18	Disagreed
9.	Acquire knowledge from ICT which has helped you to be creative to create jobs.	20	20	120	140	1.73	Disagreed
10.	Gain mastery in ICT be skillful to create jobs.	14	66	100	120	1.91	Disagreed
	Sectional Mean					1.97	Disagreed

Respondents disagreed with all items on Table 1 with the mean scores of 2.04, 2.06, 1.91, 2.18, 1.72, 2.00, 1.98, 2.18, 1.73 and 1.91 respectively that the principals did not provide ICT facilities and material resources for students to be exposed to information communication technological devices to empower you to have knowledge in job creation: acquire ICT knowledge and skills to carryout practical work independently in entrepreneurship to aid them in creating jobs; be trained to be competent in the usage of ICT to create jobs; Be trained to get information from Whatsapp to help them you in job. Create, apply devices such as google, chrome, AI and GBT to get entrepreneurial information for job creation; apply ICT device such as digital camera to televise and learn practical work which and you in job creation; use

devices like DVD player and CD ROMS to help you to retrieve entrepreneurial information for job creation; acquire practical knowledge on how to store data in the data base programmed system to help you in job creation, acquire knowledge from ICT which has helped you to be creative and innovative; gain mastery in ICT and be skillful to create jobs. All the respondents disagreed on the principals involvement in youths acquisition of information communication technological (ICT) skills for job creation in public senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada, FCT, Abuja with the sectional mean score of 1.97.

Question 2: Have principals in senior secondary schools involved in youths' acquisition of entrepreneurial skills for job creation?

Table 2: Principals Involvement in Youths Acquisition of Entrepreneurial Skill for Job Creation

S/N	Items on Principal Involvement in Youths Acquisition of Entrepreneurial Skills for Job Creation	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Decision
	Your principals have provided ICT facilities and material resources for students to:						
1	Learn and master entrepreneurial skills to create jobs	18	33	86	163	1.69	Disagreed
2	Acquire the entrepreneurship skill to independently start a business	27	25	116	132	1.82	Disagreed
3	Have technical ability to carry out new venture on personal project	30	42	123	105	1.99	Disagreed
4	Be knowledgeable to bear risk when starting a new entrepreneurship business or job	36	29	111	124	1.92	Disagreed
5	Be skillful on methods and procedures to produce entrepreneurship jobs which yield profit	24	26	118	112	1.74	Disagreed
6	Master the skill of coordinating the activities you use in creating new jobs	46	19	124	111	2.00	Disagreed
7	Have competence to organize resources and control human beings on the job.	23	44	102	123	1.84	Disagreed
8	Have the knowledge and skill to relate cordially with your employees	40	34	130	96	2.06	Disagreed
9	Have the skill to motivate your employees	12	66	100	120	1.91	Disagreed
10	Have the ability to set your objectives high when creating new jobs	24	83	117	76	2.18	Disagreed
						1.92	Disagreed

All the respondents disagreed with the items in table 2 with the mean scores of 1.69, 1.82, 1.99, 1.92, 1.74, 2.00, 1.91 and 2.18 respectively that principals have provided ICT facilities and material resources for the students to: learn and master entrepreneurial skills to create jobs, acquire the skill to independently start a business, have technical ability to carry out new venture on personal project, be knowledgeable to bear risk when starting a new entrepreneurship business or job, be skillful on methods and procedures to produce entrepreneurship jobs which yield profit, master the skill of coordinating the activities you use in creating new entrepreneurship jobs; have competence to organize resources and control human beings on the job, have the knowledge and skill to relate cordially with your employees, and have the skill to motivate your employees, have the ability to set your objectives high when

creating new jobs. All the respondents disagreed on the principals' involvement in youths' acquisition of entrepreneurial skills for job creation in public senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada, FCT, Abuja.

Discussion

The first finding proved that principals were not involved in youths' acquisition of Information Communication Technological (ICT) skills for job creation in public senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada, FCT, Abuja. Lifelong learning programs in ICT reduce youth idleness and foster job creation, mitigating social vices (Ebuk & Abdullahi, 2023). This neglect reflects broader gaps in leadership support for TPACK development, where principals fail to model technology

integration essential for youth job readiness (Chukwuemeka, 2025; Ohiare-Udebu & Chukwuemeka, 2024). So principals of secondary schools should be very much involved in the youths learning ICT so that they achieve all the benefits it offers them to be relevant in the society. Amadi (2019) affirmed that technology is the use of scientific knowledge and ideas to carryout practical works to produce materials which will help in job creation. Hence, principals should help the youths acquire this scientific knowledge so as to help them create jobs for themselves and others.

The second study finding proved that principals were not involved in youths' acquisition of entrepreneurial skills for job creation. Amadi (2019) posited that having entrepreneurship skills will help the youths to be creative, innovative to be engaged in job creation and that it will increase production to boost the nation's economy. Vesenyi (2016) maintained that youths should acquire entrepreneurial skills to start and manage new businesses, create and implement new initiatives and execute right decisions while on the job. Principals should get involved in order to provide appropriate entrepreneurship facilities which will aid the youths to learn and acquire mastery and competence in

entrepreneurship to establish, enhance and increase more jobs.

Conclusion

The study concluded that the principals did not involve themselves in youths' acquisition of ICT and entrepreneurial skills for job creation.

Recommendations

The researcher recommended based on the findings of the study that:

1. The principals should ensure that the youths are well educated to acquire knowledge, skill and competence on ICT and entrepreneurship so as to be able to create jobs for themselves and others in the society. This will make these youths to be self-reliant, independent and relevant in the society. They should do this by ensuring that the schools have functional and enough equipment, facilities, qualified instructors, educational and material resources for ICT and entrepreneurship education to thrive.

Governments at all levels should encourage the schools management by supporting them with funds to make sure that ICT and entrepreneurship education is taken and executed seriously. Underfunding exacerbates youth unemployment and socio-economic gaps (Abdullahi & Muhammad, 2019), making state investment urgent. The youths must be trained to be able to create jobs opportunities to boost the economy of the nation.

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